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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

THE SIBYL IN MALACCA: A JOURNEY OF AN APENNINE LEGEND TO EAST INDIES¹

1. The Sibyl of the Apennines across Europe and beyond

Sure enough, the readers of the present series of articles, *The Apennine Sibyl, a Mystery and a Legend*, are fully accustomed to the tale and mood of the Sibyl of the Apennines: an oracle and a prophetess, an illustrious queen and a lascivious, seductive host, who according to an ancient legend would reside within the rocky bowels of a remote Italian mountain, which raises its crowned mountain-top amid the many peaks of the Apennines, between the regions of Umbria and Marche. From Andrea da Barberino's and Antoine de la Sale's fifteenth-century literary works, which described with magical accents the Sibyl's concealed abode and her fairy retinue, a multitude of men of letters, geographers, scholars and researchers have confronted with her legendary tradition, in significant connection with the neighbouring, equally-sinister tale concerning Pontius Pilate and his

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gloomy lake, lying only a few miles away within the very same mountainous range. For centuries the Sibyl's Cave, secluded amid high cliffs as it was, has been a destination of choice for travellers coming from all over Europe, in search of a fascinating mystery, a sensual hidden realm, a place for consecrating spellbooks and a gateway to some sort of otherworldly land.

The Apennine Sibyl and her eerie tale: a tradition that, for the first time ever, with the article *The chthonian legend* (2020), was put in conjectural connection with the peculiar seismic behaviour of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

So the legendary tradition concerning a Sibyl living amid the Italian Apennines was widely known all across the European continent, having travelled through France, Germany, Flanders and as far as the British Isles, as attested by the many literary references mentioned in various articles published within the series *The Apennine Sibyl, a Mystery and a Legend*.

Fig. 1 - Mount Sibyl in Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* (Antwerp, 1603), table following p. 86

But what about countries outside Europe? Can we find any references to the Apennine Sibyl in different, far-away territories? Perhaps, in other continents, too?

Incredibly enough, the answer seems to be in the affirmative. And, even more incredibly, the place in which we are going to retrieve, almost unexpectedly, a reference to our Sibyl is located very far from the Apennines.

Beyond a continent, across an ocean. We are about to fly away from Italy and Europe, preparing to land in a region and town we would never have imagined before.

There, amid the mist of centuries, we touch the ground at a specific point in time: in the year 1613.

And the town we have just reached is Malacca, East Indies.

2. Seventeenth-century Malacca: a strategical port towards the East, China and the Pacific

Malacca, the historical town and port located in modern Malaysia, facing the narrowest stretch of the Strait which bears its same name, the island of Sumatra lying just in front: a sentinel sitting on the Malay Peninsula and a gateway to the isles set further to the east, Borneo and Java and the Philippines and many others.

For centuries maritime trade has been unfolding before its very shores, merchant ships sailing to and from trading ports across Europe, Asia and the Pacific Ocean, and crossing the Strait of Malacca to reach their destinations, stowed with loads of spices and other valuable goods. From the original foundation by a local prince, in the fifteenth century it became a protectorate of imperial China, then a Portuguese colony following the military conquest by Afonso de Albuquerque in 1511. In 1641 the town fell under Dutch rule, which lasted until the British came in during the first quarter of the nineteenth century, in application of an agreement with the Netherlands.

Novelist Joseph Conrad, in his tale *The end of the tether*, recounted his own experience as a trade ship officer navigating the Malacca's waters,

describing the «monotonous huckster's round, up and down the Straits», a route which always presented, as a fascinating sight, «Malacca to begin with, in at daylight and out at dusk, to cross over with a rigid phosphorescent wake this highway of the Far East». A romantic, exotic sight for an European enamoured of East Indies: «Darkness and gleams on the water, clear stars on a black sky, perhaps the lights of a home steamer keeping her unswerving course in the middle...».

In 1613 Malacca is still under full Portuguese control. It is in this year that Manuel Godinho de Erédia, a cartographer serving as a military engineer under the Viceroy of Portuguese India, and based at the time in Goa, published its extensive *Description of Malaca, Meridional India, and Cathay* (*Declaraçam de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay*), a complete illustration of the many islands, populations and customs that were to be encountered in a region of the world set between the Indian and Pacific Oceans.

Fig. 2 - Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaraçam de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613)
(manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels)

De Erédia knew markedly well Malacca and its surroundings: not only he was born there in 1563, he had also served in the town for four years,

starting from 1600, managing the military defence, strengthening the local fortress, commanding a fleet of Portuguese armed vessels and carrying out exploration surveys to the inland, for map drawing and prospecting purposes.

Fig. 3 - The fortress of Malacca at the time of Portuguese rule, from António Bocarro's *Livro das plantas de todas as fortalezas, cidades e povoaçoens do Estado da India Oriental* (1635), drawing between folia 146 and 147 (manuscript BPE COD. CXV/2-1 preserved at the Biblioteca Pública de Évora, Portugal)

Permicuri, the king-founder of Malacca, writes Manuel Godinho de Erédia, «fortified himself on the crest of the hill [...] he employed the greatest industry and energy in extending the town on both sides of the river: and he developed his new state by establishing commerce and traffic with the surrounding peoples [...] Then, when the port was open and frequented [...] it attracted] the strangers from the surrounding islands, who peopled the port and popularized it, bringing their merchandise and exchanging their gold and spices for cloths. This trade made Malaca one of the richest and most opulent States in the world».

[In the original Portuguese text: «... deque ficou Aquelle estado o mays oppulento e rico do Mundo»].

Fig. 4 - Malacca as «estado o mays oppulento e rico do Mundo» in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaraçam de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèquẽ Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folium 5

The description of Malacca provided by de Erédia is extensive and quite comprehensive: in his *Declaraçam* the Portuguese illustrates a number of topics including Malacca's town and districts, the flora and fauna, the etymology of local names, the military infrastructures, trade and commerce, and many other aspects of this portion of the Malay Peninsula.

As reported by J.V. Mills in the introductory note to his English translation of the *Declaraçam*, contained in the *Journal of the Malayan Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society* (Vol. III, Singapore 1930), de Erédia was the son of a Portuguese adventurer and a princess from Celebes, one of the Greater Sunda Islands. In his early years de Erédia attended the College of the Company of Jesus in Malacca, then in Goa (where St. Francis Xavier, a founder of the Company, was active a few decades earlier), joining the ranks of the Company at the age of sixteen, though he left the Jesuits just a few years later.

The classical, Greek and Roman studies promoted by the Company of Jesus within their educational system, which will be summarised in their

famous *Ratio atque Institutio Studiorum Societatis Iesu* a few years later, were a fundamental part of de Erédia's cultural horizon, and we will find many traces of this in the *Declaração*. A first instance is the Portuguese's mention of the ancient name of the area of Malacca:

«Today's Samatta [Sumatra] is an island 600 leagues in circumference, whereas in olden times it was a peninsula or Chersonese (which means a land which is joined to another land by an Isthmus); as in fact was the case in the time of Ptolemy, in the year 163 after the birth of Christ our Saviour, 1248 years before the foundation of the town of Malaca».

[In the original Portuguese text: «... sendo antigamente Peninsula ou Chersonese ... como era na verdade em tempo de Ptholomeo ano 163 depois do Nascimento de Christo Nosso Salvador...»].

Fig. 5 - Ptolemy and the Chersonese in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folium 13

And here is the «Chersonese called by Ptolemy the Golden Chersonese owing to its richness in gold» (in the original Portuguese text: «chamado par Ptholomeo chersonese Aureo por ser Muy Fertil de ouro»). We can see it as it appears in a magnificent fifteenth-century version of Ptolemy's *Cosmographia*, with its golden letters proudly stating «Aurea Chersonesus» on a peninsula protruding from the land of Malaysia, in the area of Malacca, and possibly to be identified as modern Sumatra, known since antiquity for its gold deposits.

Fig. 6 - The «Aurea Chersonesus» depicted in an edition of Ptolemy's *Cosmographia* published by Jacobus Angelus in the second half of fifteenth century (manuscript Ms-981 réserve preserved at the Bibliothèque de l'Arsenal, Paris, folia 117v-118r)

Actually Manuel Godinho de Erédia includes in his work a number of classical references: for instance, he quotes from Aristotle's *Meteorologica* when talking about the metals used by the natives to shape their weapons; and, in a section dedicated to local «Sorceresses» («Feyticeiras»), he writes that «other enchantresses transform themselves from women into the form of lizards and other animals and birds, in order to do evil, like the ancient Syrce», introducing a mention of Circe, the famous sorceress appearing in Homer's *Odyssey* and Vergil's *Aeneid*, adding that magical arts «in antiquity were punished by Emperor Nero».

Fig. 7 - Aristotle and Circe as they appear in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaraçam de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folia 21 and 38

In this framework, marked by a tangible attention to both classical themes and local folklore, the latter annotated with references to Greek-Roman mythology and literature, it is no surprise to find in de Erédia's *Declaração* a fascinating description of one of the most renowned legendary tales which has been living, for many centuries, in the Malay Peninsula.

And this description of a local fairy tale will be colored and highlighted by de Erédia, for the enjoyment of his readers, with references to another tale, which presents sound links to the classical world and traditions.

The local fairy tale is the “Puteri Gunung Ledang” (“Princess of Mount Ophir”); while the tale coming from a distant, far-away place is that of the Sibyl. Possibly, the Sibyl of the Apennines.

3. *A magical mountain, cave and queen in the Malay Peninsula*

«The mountain of Gunoledam, as Mount Atlas or the Sybilline caves, is a lofty mountain half a league in height and rather more than a league in circumference at the base», he writes. «It rises in isolation, there being no other mountain in the surrounding country...».

[In the original Portuguese text: «Monte de gunoledam, como outro monte Atlante, ou cavas Sybillas, [?] um monte alteroso de Meja legoa de alto...»].

Fig. 8 - Mount Gunoledam and the caves of the Sibyl as they appear in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folia 32r and 32v

This is the beginning of Chapter 15 of de Erédia's work, wholly dedicated to a magical montain lying not far from the town of Malacca. An enchanted Malaysian mountain which is immediatly put in touch, by the Portuguese writer, with the sibilline lore in Europe.

But what sort of mountain is this?

Mount Gunoledam is an existing elevation: it is known today as Gunung Ledang (“gunung” meaning “mountain”), or Mount Ophir. It lies 25 miles northeast of Malacca, with its tree-covered mountain-top raising up to 4,186 feet. Trekkers from all around the world come to this charming tourist destination, which offers a commanding view of the Strait of Malacca.

Fig. 9 - Gunung Ledang (Mount Ophir) in the Tangkak District, Johor, Malaysia

Why a seventeenth-century Portuguese author did want to include a mention of this specific mountain in his description of the Malacca region? And for what reason did he compare Gunung Ledang to some sort of «Sybilline caves»?

Fig. 10 - Mount Gunoledam from a map contained in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folium 11v

Let's continue our exploration of the de Erédia's *Declaração* (with the help of J.V. Mills' translation) to find out that «Gunoledam» appears to be a very special mountain:

«To this mountain (according to the story of the Malays) retired the Queen Putry, companion of Permicuri, founder of Malacca. Here the enchanted Putry remains for ever immortal and here she lives to this day by her magical arts».

[In the original Portuguese text: «En este Monte (conforme a fabula de Maleios) se recolhea aquella Putry Raynha companheira de Permicuri, fundador de Malaca: onde a ditto Putry encantada permaneo sempre imortal com Vida ate o presente por Arte Magica»].

So at the beginning of the seventeenth century a legendary tale lived in this mountainous area: a sort of tale we already know, a tale which narrates of a

magical, immortal queen and enchantress who resides within an enchanted mountain. Immediately, a marked sense of déjà vu seizes our mind, bringing back to us the well-known image of our Apennine Sibyl, concealed in a cave set beneath the cliff of Mount Sibyl, in central Italy.

Fig. 11 - Queen Putry in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folium 32v

Of course, all this does not necessarily imply the envisagement of any direct connection between the two legends, the Malay and the Italian, in terms of origin or parenthood (but wait for the very end of this paper to be shown a very different conclusion...); nonetheless, we will see that a link, based on some manifest similarities shared by the two tales, will be possibly established by the same de Erédia, together with another authors, thus building up an almost incredible bridge which crosses more than 6,000 miles, from the Apennines to Malacca.

The Malay legend, as decribed by Manuel Godinho de Erédia, is just as fascinating as the Italian one:

Fig. 12 - Queen Putry's cave and appearance in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folium 32v

«She makes her home in a Cave and hollow on the summit of the mountain, and here she lies on a bed readied with dead men's bones: in this she appears as a beautiful young damsel, [adorned] with silk and gold».

[In the original Portuguese text: «Aqual tem sua habitação no alto da quelle Monte em Sua Caverna e concavidade de em que esta sobre [?] leito armado de ossos de mortos: emque representa aforma de Moça donzela hermosa e [?] de seda e ouro»].

Queen Putry lives her immortal life in a cave hidden within a mountain. She takes the form of a most beautiful woman, her abode is a sort of pleasant heaven (the cave's hollow is encircled by «thickets of bamboo, from which proceed harmonious voices and sounds of flutes and other musical instruments, [...and] trees bearing delicious fruits of every kind [...resounding with] the harmonious songs of birds»). However, the presence of human bones tells the eerie tale of a seductive, dangerous enchantress:

«Farther away from this grove are the forests occupied by tigers who guard the Queen Putry, enchanted like another Syrce or the Thessalian».

[In the original Portuguese text: «... encantada como outra Syrce ou Thesalica»].

Fig. 13 - Queen Putry as Greek enchantress Circe in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folium 32v

Here Manuel Godinho de Erédia returns to his classical cultural background by comparing a Malay enchantress, Queen Putry, to most famous characters of the Greek and Roman literary traditions: Circe, whom he also mentioned in the chapter dedicated to sorceresses («Feytíceiras»); and Erichtho, the appalling Thessalian witch described by first-century

Latin author Marcus Annaeus Lucanus in his *Pharsalia*, a necromancer with a ghastly connection with the dead and the Netherworld.

But this is not all. Because de Erédia pushes his comparison to Western enchantresses even further. And the Sibyls, already mentioned by the Portuguese author at the very beginning of this section dedicated to Mount Gunoledam, make their reappearance in the text:

«This story must be a fairy-tale: but the natives regard it as true. For they assert that on the mountain of Gunoledam there is a certain cavern, like those Pythian and Sibyls' caves, where the wild Banuas learn the magic arts, and hold communication with the devil in the dark caverns».

[In the original Portuguese text: «... como Aquellas cavas Pitias e Sebillas...»].

Fig. 14 - The «Pythian and Sibyls' caves» in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folium 32v

Now Queen Putry and her cavern are mentioned in relation to other most-famous classical characters we know very well: the oracular priestess serving at the Temple of Apollo in Delphi, the Pythia; and an unnamed Sibyl, or Sibyls, delivering oracles in some subterranean hollows. Both are mentioned in connection with necromantic rituals, which at Mount Gunoledang were performed by a local ethnic group, the Banuas (de Erédia described them in Chapter 2 as «a race as wild as the satyrs of Pliny»).

De Erédia intends to highlight two specific features which mark the Malay sorceress. The first feature is linked to the healing powers of sorcery:

«[The Banuas] hear the voice which reveals the virtues of the miraculous medicinal plants and herbs, as well as the methods of preparation and the proportions of component substances which are effectual for producing different results, beneficial and harmful».

A second feature is related to the sorceress' capability to transform herself into any animal shape she wishes:

«Putry, who, like the Thessalian Eritho, magician and sorceress, or like Syrcce the enchantress, changed from the form of a woman to that of animals and birds, according to the doctrine of Tages».

Fig. 15 - Putry's transformation skills in Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* (1613) (manuscript no. 7264 cat. 7447 preserved at the Bibliothèque Royale du Belgique, Brussels), folium 32v

In this excerpt we find additional references to Erichtho and Circe, a mention of Tages (Etruscan deity of divination), and - concealed amid so many elements - a potential, interesting hint to the traits that mark another leading figure within the medieval sibilline lore, as we will detail later in this paper.

Here ends the tale of Queen Putry and Mount Gunung Ledang as recounted in 1613 by Manuel Godinho de Erédia: a Portuguese cartographer and engineer enamoured of Malacca, its people and the magical stories narrated to him.

Clearly enough, the learned author, born from a Portuguese adventurer and a local princess, could not abstain from being captured by the enchantment of a narrative which seemed to have more than a single point of contact with the myths and legends he already knew from his cultural homeland, including the Greek-Roman tradition and, possibly, something more, even though somewhat shady and elusive.

For it blatantly appears that de Erédia, in 1613, has in his mind a Sibyl, to whom he likes to compare the Malaysian tale of Queen Putry.

But which Sibyl is this? Does he refer to the Delphic Sibyl, with his mention of the Pythia? Or, perhaps, to the Cimmerian, who also presented necromantic traits and was a subterranean oracle?

We intend now to explore the chance that his thought may have been directed towards a different Sibyl, one who is not included in the classical list of ten.

Because, possibly, Manuel Godinho de Erédia, in 1613, was thinking of the Apennine Sibyl.

4. Queen Putry, an ancient, popular legend in the Malay Peninsula

Before we proceed into the sibilline issue we just outlined, let's summarize the main aspects, history and success of the tale which concerns Queen Putry, sorceress and enchanter.

As described by Menon, J. Y., Shunmugam, K., and Ramalingam, S. in their paper *Intersemiotic Translation: Mat Dollah's Batik Paintings of the Malay Folktale "Puteri Gunung Ledang"* (Journal of Communication, Language and Culture, 4(2), 2024) - to whom I wish here to express my thanks for this most interesting article, which gave me the chance to know about this fascinating Malaysian tale and so write the present paper - «amongst the heritage of Malaysia's folktales, the tale of "Puteri Gunung Ledang", also known as the "Princess of Mount Ophir" remains the most iconic in the present day. Immortalised in numerous retellings and adaptations, movies, artwork, poems and stories, the mythical princess was even featured on miniature stamp sheets to commemorate the richness of Malaysia's folk stories in 2014». «Forever linked to the golden era of the Malacca dynasty», they add, «she is commonly depicted in literature as the ethereal fairy princess who refused the marriage proposal of a king by setting impossible conditions for him to fulfil».

According to scholars, the earliest retrievable source of the Queen Putry's tale is to be found in *Sejarah Melayu (The Malay Annals)*, a chronicle contained in manuscript Raffles MS 18 and possibly dating back to 1535 or

even before (even though other scholars reconsider it as possibly having been edited in the first quarter of the seventeenth century).

Fig. 16 - The excerpt on the Princess of Gunong Ledang from *Sejarah Melayu* (*The Malay Annals*), manuscript Raffles MS 18 (Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland, London), opening folium and folium 131

Following the *Sejarah Melayu*, which we read from the English translation edited by C.C. Brown in 1953, we find Sultan Mansur Shah, Raja of Malacca, expressing his desire «to ask for the hand of the Princess of Gunong Ledang». So the Raja's envoy and his retinue «after some days [...] reached the foot of Gunong Ledang and began the ascent of the mountain». They went through the magical «singing bamboos», which Manuel Godinho de Erédia also mentioned, finally getting to an enchanted garden. There, four women were waiting for them. The oldest one, but still a handsome lady (it will turn out that she was the Princess in disguise), «asked Tun Mamad who he was and of what country. And Tun Mamad answered, "I am a man of Malaka and I have been sent here by Sultan

Mansur Shah to ask for the hand of the Princess of Gunong Ledang in marriage'».

And the reply from the enchanted Princess is typical of fairy tales and impossible dreams:

«If the Raja of Malaka desire me, let him make for me a bridge of gold and a bridge of silver from Malaka to Gunong Ledang: and for a betrothal gift let there be seven trays of mosquitos' hearts, seven trays of mites' hearts, a vat of young areca-nut water, a vat of tears, a cup of the Raja's blood and a cup of his son's blood. On these conditions I approve the request of the Raja of Malaka».

Fig. 17 - Princess of Gunong Ledang's impossible request to the Raja of Malacca from C.C. Brown's translation of the *Sejarah Melayu* (*The Malayan Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, Vol. 25, parts 2 & 3, no. 159, 1953), p. 104

That was too much for the Sultan. As his envoy «descended Gunong Ledang to return to Malaka [...] and related to him the message they had

received from the Princess of Gunong Ledang», Mansur Shah, bewildered and even a little frightened, he could only say that «”All that she demands we can provide, save only the blood of our son; that we cannot provide, for our heart would not suffer us to take it”». And thus no marriage was celebrated between the Sultan of Malacca and the Princess of Gunong Ledang.

So went the tale of Queen Putry (but “Putry” means exactly “Princess”) of Gunung Ledang: a Malay fable which was collected by Manuel Godinho de Erédia, a Portuguese man whose mother was a princess from the Sunda islands, then crossed the centuries in various forms and versions, turning into one of the most famous legendary tales across Malaysia and Indonesia.

But what has this tale to do with classical Sibyls? Apparently nothing. And yet, it is Manuel Godinho de Erédia himself, at the beginning of the seventeenth century, who intends to establish some sort of relation with the sibylline lore, also including a possible, closer reference to the Sibyl of the Apennines.

Let's try to investigate this matter further, as we proceed into the next paragraph.

5. The sibyls of de Erédia: cryptic references and possible solutions

A fairy princess whose abode is hidden within a mountain. Magical caves and gardens. An enchanted court. This is Queen Putry of Gunung Ledang, Malaysia, seventeenth century. But we also know another tale, featuring some similarities: a magical mountain, Mount Sibyl; an enchanted court, cave and gardens; and a fairy queen, the Sibyl of the Apennines. Italy, fifteenth century.

Is there any connection between the two? Possibly just a mere resemblance of fairy narratives. Nonetheless, it is the Manuel Godinho de Erédia himself who casts on the table some sort of link between the princess of Malacca and the Sibyls. At least, the classical ones.

«Monte de gunoledam, como [...] cavas Sybillas», he writes: the mountain of Gunoledam, just like the Sybilline caves. «Como Aquellas cavas Pitias e Sebillas», he adds: like those hollows of the Pythia and the Sibyls.

So in the mind of de Erédia the Queen Putry of Gunung Ledang seems to be comparable to the legendary tradition concerning the Sibyls, and to the Pythia, the priestess who vaticinated at Delphi, Greece. There another sibilline oracle was also present, the Delphic Sibyl.

We know that fourt-century author Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius, in his *De divinis institutionibus adversus gentes*, provided a most renowned list of ten 'classical' Sibyls: «It is known that Sibyls were ten in number. Marcus Varro enumerated them all under the writers, who wrote an account of each. The first was from the Persians, and of her Nicanor made mention, who wrote the deeds of Alexander of Macedon. The second was of Libya, and of her Euripides made mention in the prologue of the Lamia. The third of Delphi...».

Fig. 18 - The excerpt on the Sibyls as it appears in a most valuable edition of Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius *De Divinis Institutionibus*, printed in 1465 at the benedictine abbey of Subiaco (Italy)

But which one was Manuel Godinho de Erédia thinking of?

Was he possibly referring to the Delphic Sibyl? This might be the case, as the Pythia served the oracle of Apollo in Delphi entering the innermost premises of the temple, the *adyton*: there, a cleft in the rock gave way to the *pneuma*, maybe vapors with intoxicating effects. However, no caves were there, and still today it is not clear to scholars whether the *adyton* was a subterranean room, or not. Furthermore, the Pythia and the Delphic Sibyl are different figures, the latter possibly predating the former, and with no caves associated to her.

Another possible candidate for de Erédia sibilline reference is the Cumaean Sibyl, who prophesised in Cumae, not far from Naples, in Italy: the seventh oracle in Lactantius' classical list. Of course, the Portuguese writer, a former Jesuit, perfectly knew the verses written by Vergilius in Book 6 of his *Aeneid*: «terrific riddles she yells, as she sings in her cave, the truth enshrouded in darkness» [«Cumaea Sibylla - horrendas canit ambages antroque remugit - obscuris vera involvens» in Latin].

This is a cave for a Sibyl; just as other caves were referred to another Sibyl, the Cimmerian, fourth in the classical list, and companion to the Cumaean (the latter a possible earlier version of the former): she was an oracle associated with the ancient population of Cimmerians, who lived in the area of Cumae in dark, subterranean abodes.

So did de Erédia intended to refer to the Cumaean / Cimmerian Sibyl?

Certainly we cannot rule out this simple possibility.

However, we think the most probable solution is not so easily found.

In fact, we must consider that neither the Cumaean nor the Cimmerian have nothing to do with princesses, queens and magical courts. And with no mountains, either.

Thus we are forced to get back to our initial surmise: may de Erédia have intended to refer to the Apennine Sibyl, ruling her magical court in central Italy, within a cave set beneath an enchanted mountain, Mount Sibyl?

As we already know, the Sibyl of the Apennines is not included in the classical list set out by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius. Nonetheless, Manuel Godinho de Erédia writes in 1613, and at that time the Apennine Sibyl was a sort of 'success story', being widely known amidst men of letters, learned aristocrats and an opaque necromantic milieu, since the first half of the fifteenth century (with the works written by Andrea da Barberino, Antoine de la Sale, Flavio Biondo, Felix Hemmerlin) and throughout the sixteenth (with the publication as a printed version of de la Sale's manuscripted account, the evocative description provided by Leandro Alberti, the gloomy references included in their works by clerics such as Pierre Crespet and Martino Delrio).

But did de Erédia know about that elusive Sibyl, never quoted by Lactantius nor by any other classical author? In principle, we might just assume that no word about the Apennine Sibyl, a legend originating from Italy, had ever reached that far-away portion of the globe, the East Indies. In addition to that, we must also remember that de Erédia was born in 1563 in Malacca and lived his entire life in that area of the world, as he never travelled to Europe.

So did he know about that renowned Sibyl? The answer is yes. For certain he knew about that distant Sibyl, lost amid the Italian Apennines.

But how can this be? There are multiple reasons for that.

First, as we already noted quoting from J.V. Mills, Manuel Godinho de Erédia received his education with the Company of Jesus. As reported in the short biography he himself included in his *Tratado ophirico*, a work dedicated to the biblical topic concerning King Salomon and the mythical eastern territory of Ophir, dating to 1616, in his childhood he attended the College of the Jesuits in Malacca («no collegio de companhia de Iesu de Malaca»). At the age of 13, he was sent to Goa at the Seminary of the Company of Jesus («...Goa, onde se recolheo no Seminario...»), where he studied «a gramatica, Artes, Philosophia, Geometrias, sciencias e Mathematicas».

Fig. 20 - The entries relating to Flavio Biondo, Leandro Alberti and Martino Delrio in an eighteenth-century catalogue of the *Biblioteca Major* of the Company of Jesus at the Collegio Romano in Rome (manuscripts Ant.Cat.23/2, Ant.Cat.23/1 and Ant.Cat.23/5, Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, 1750-1800), folia 96r, 29v and 15r respectively

For a man like de Erédia, who since his youth «devoted to the service of cosmography, with the title of Major Cosmographer of the State» (as he himself writes in the *Tratado ophirico*), the availability, possibly at the Jesuit college in Malacca and the seminar in Goa, of the most captivating geographical treatises on Italy written by Flavio Biondo and Leandro Alberti, must have been a sort of bounty offered to him by the Company's educational system: no doubt he surely had the chance not only to retrieve copies of them both, but also to read them cravingly from beginning to end, as modern heirs of the classical geographical tradition established by Ptolemy, a beloved author extensively quoted by the Portuguese in his *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* and the *Tratado ophirico*.

And we must not forget that, amid the many geographical works published between the end of the sixteenth century and the beginning of the seventeenth, we find the fundamental atlas released by Abraham Ortelius: the *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum*, with its bounty of maps, which Major

Cosmographer Manuel Godinho de Erédia certainly could not have overlooked in his passionate studies of geography, and including a large map which shows the «Aurea Chersonesus sive peninsula» according to the classical description provided by Ptolemy.

Fig. 21 - The region of Malaysia and Sumatra as they appear in Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* (Antwerp, 1603), section dedicated to ancient geography, f. 36

Does Ortelius mention the Apennine Sibyl in his atlas? Of course he does.

As we detailed in our previous paper *Four years from the Chthonian legend*, a map of the "Marcha Anconae", known as "Picenum", shows the accurate location of Mount Sibyl. In addition to that, a comprehensive caption tells the reader that «in this place, looming over the mentioned territory, where the Apennine Mountain Range exceeds itself with the most elevated peaks, that ghastly Cavern is found whose name is Sibyl's (people calls it the "Sibyl's Cave") and the Elysium is supposed to be there. The populace also likes to believe that in this Cave of the Sibyl a large kingdom exists, full of magnificent, kingly palaces and enchanting gardens, and sensual maidens and every kind of delightful pleasures in great abundance...» [In the original Latin text: «Apenninus mons hoc loco, ubi huic regioni imminet, editissimis iugis se ipsam superat, in quibus Antrum illud horribile est quod Sibyllae cognominant (Grotta de la Sibylla vulgo)...»].

Fig. 22 - The caption on Mount Sibyl in Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* (Antwerp, 1603), p. 86

No need to say, the *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* by Ortelius was well known to Jesuits and had its place on the shelves of the *Biblioteca Major* at the Collegio Romano in Rome.

Fig. 23 - The entry relating to Abraham Ortelius in an eighteenth-century catalogue of the *Biblioteca Major* of the Company of Jesus at the Collegio Romano in Rome (manuscript Ant.Cat.23/9, Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale di Roma, 1750-1800), folium 16v

So can we assume that Manuel Godinho de Erédia actually knew about the existence of a legendary tradition concerning a Sibyl of the Apennines, residing in a cave set within a mountain which raised its peak near the town of Norcia, Italy?

We think this can be almost undisputedly assumed. And for another reason, too.

Because de Erédia, indeed, was born from a Portuguese father and a mother-princess of East Indies. But its veins, unexpected as it may appear, also carried Italian blood. And this blood was from central Italy, not far from Mount Sibyl.

It is in the *Tratado ophirico* that de Erédia tells the readers about his own origin: he says that he himself was «the son of Juan de Heredia de Aquaviva, on one side from Lourenço Fernandez de Heredia of the noble family of Dom Phelippede Heredia, count of Fuentes in the region of Aragon; and on the other side from Juan Francisco Aquaviva of the noble family of the Duke of Atri and Prince of Teramo».

Fig. 24 - Manuel Godinho de Erédia's lineage from *Tratado Ophirico* (manuscript Portugais 44, Bibliothèque nationale de France, 1616), folium 62r

The Aquaviva, or, in Italian, the Acquaviva family ruled the Duchy of Atri, in the Italian region of Abruzzo, for many centuries starting from 1395, with repeated claims over and conflicts with the neighbouring town of Teramo. The two towns, Atri and Teramo lie just some 35 miles southeast of the Sibillini Mountain Range, where Mount Sibyl raises its crowned

cliff. No wonder if, within the Italian branch of de Erédia's family, the legendary narratives concerning the Apennine Sibyl may have been known and told, even though we don't know whether the Portuguese cartographer, living as he did in the East Indies, used to maintain any contacts by letter with his relatives in Italy; or possibly, he had heard about the magical, fairy tale of Mount Sibyl when he was a child, just as it occurred to Leandro Alberti («... as I myself happened to hear in my father's house, when I was a small child, for the thrilled entertainment of women»). Nonetheless, this is another hint to the chance that Manuel Godinho de Erédia knew of that far-away Italian Sibyl, with her gloomy cave and all the fascination that that sinister, enchanting tale brought with itself.

We also like to add here a further suggestion, which is no proof of de Erédia's actual intention to refer to the Sibyl of the Apennines, though it opens the way to evocative connections with the legendary path that led to the birth of this medieval Sibyl, not included in the classical list.

And this suggestion arises from de Erédia's mention of Erichtho. And Morgan.

Sure enough, the mention he writes about Erichtho is just to be read as a mere comparison between Queen Putry and the Thessalian witch depicted in Lucanus' *Pharsalia*, with necromantic features that, according to the Portuguese, appear to be shared by both legendary characters.

However, we must remember that Erichtho played an important role in the generation of the figure of the Apennine Sibyl, as we detailed in our previous paper *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*. At the end of the twelfth century, German poet Hartmann von Aue, in his poem *Erec*, established for the first time a close relationship between Morgan le Fay, the enchanter belonging to the Matter of Britain, with her powers as necromancer and sorceress, and the classical world, with its Sibyls and the witch Erichtho:

«Since the Sybil died, and Erictho perished, of which Lucanus tells us, and sorcery which they could command had died away ages ago, with her it all came back (about which I don't want to say much at this time, since it would take too long). Since then, the earthly realm probably has had no better mistress of the magic arts than Morgan le Fay...»

[In the original Old German text: «Seyt daz sibilla erstarb - vnd Ericto verdarb - von der vns Lucanuf zalt - daz jr zauberlich gewalt - wem fy wolte gepot - der dauor was lanng todt - daz er erstund wol gefunt - von der ich euch hie zestund - nu nicht mer fagen wil - wann es wurde ze vil - sy gewan das erdtrich - das wisset warlich - von zauberlichen fynne - nie besser maisterynne - dann Famurgan...»].

Hartmann von Aue's work traces the moment in which 'Sebile', a character appearing within the Matter of Britain, a companion and alternative identity of Morgan, begins her centuries-long travel across romances and poems gradually acquiring the traits of a necromantic Sibyl, with her court and palaces hidden under the protective cover of a magical spell, and eventually within an enchanted mountain (first Mount Etna, and then the Apennines), as we saw in our previous article *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*.

Did Manuel Godinho de Erédia know anything about Hartmann von Aue? We don't think so. As we assumed earlier in this paragraph, we think that de Erédia knew about the Apennine Sibyl's lore and fairy tales, which were renowned and widely circulating in the seventeenth century; however, his mentions of Erichtho and Morgan show that his mind was moving around, and thinking of, the very same aspects that marks the figure of the Apennine Sibyl, with all the dark, hellish hues which enshroud this later, non-classical Sibyl: an offspring of Morgan le Fay combined with traits drawn from the Cumaean and Cimmerian Sibyls, with their necromantic powers, and the impious, ghastly Erichtho.

Morgan le Fay: the sorceress who could change her shape at will, as reported by Geoffrey of Monmouth in the twelfth century («she also knows an art by which to change her shape...»), and restated in the same century by Hartmann von Aue: «she lived just as she wished; in the air or on earth - if she wanted she could sleep on the waves or live underwater [...] if she wanted, she could turn someone into a bird or animal...». An ability that Queen Putry, too, possessed: «Putry, who, like the Thessalian Eritho, magician and sorceress, or like Syrce the enchantress, changed from the form of a woman to that of animals and birds», writes de Erédia.

Just as all the listed characters, Queen Putry of Gunung Ledang, too, for Manuel Godinho de Erédia, was part of a gloomy lore, which men

happened to develop in their hearts in different parts of the world: East Indies, like the Italian Apennines or Thessaly in Greece.

Getting back to our main question, we have to consider again, in the light we described above, the words written by de Erédia.

Sibyls and caves. Caves and Sibyls. «Monte de gunoledam, como [...] cavas Sybillas [...] Como Aquellas cavas Pitias e Sebillas». When writing about the Gunung Ledang, did de Erédia have in his mind the cave hidden beneath the cliff of Mount Sibyl? Did he think of the Sibyl of the Apennines?

We think this might possibly be the case.

However, as de Erédia did not write that Sibyl's appellation, nor provided any other clue about her closer identification, we need to turn to another source that may help direct our steps towards the right direction.

Because we have another source. A literary source which even predates Manuel Godinho de Erédia's *Declaração*.

This is another Portuguese, another experienced man who lived his adventurous life between East Indies and China.

This is Tomé Pires. And he, just like de Erédia, wrote an interesting remark on Gunung Ledang. And Sibyls.

6. Tomé Pires, the Princess of Gunung Ledang and an Italian Sibyl

Tomé Pires was born in Lisbon around 1470, just a few years before Portuguese explorer Bartolomeu Dias crossed the Cape of Good Hope in 1488, opening the way to East Indies and the lucrative trade of spices, and therefore laying the foundations of the fortune of the Kingdom of Portugal for the years to come.

Tomé Pires was an apothecary at the court of the King: possibly one of the best jobs at the time, since the newly-acquired colonies needed experienced

men like him to manage the spice trade, by sending the goods all the way back to Portugal and Europe for a business that proved to be as rich as gold.

Fig. 25 - The first page of Tomé Pires' *Suma oriental* (manuscript 1248, Bibliothèque de l'Assemblée Nationale de France, Paris, sixteenth century), folium 117r

So, at the age of forty, he was requested to travel to India. From there, in 1512 he was sent right to Malacca, conquered by Portuguese admiral Afonso de Albuquerque just a year earlier. A manager, or 'factor', taking care of the spice trade was urgently needed there, as Malacca was already a major port and exchange market for huge quantities of spice goods, and the

Portuguese needed to have a reliable and experienced professional in the town.

His stay there lasted less than three years, as in 1515 he was appointed ambassador of Portugal to China out of the merits acquired during his service in Malacca. Nonetheless, despite the short duration of his residence in the Malay port, Tomé Pires wrote an extensive manuscripted work, containing most valuable information on the eastern routes to the spice trade and East Indies: the *Suma Oriental*, a milestone treatise, completed in 1515, which provides a comprehensive illustration of the history, geography, populations, plants, and trade routes of an area that, at that time, was still almost unknown to European scholars.

Of this work a single, precious manuscripted copy was found in Paris in 1937. From it we read the words written by Tomé Pires, with the help of the valuable Portuguese transcript and translation into English edited by Armando Cortesão, who was also the discoverer of the manuscript.

In his treatise, full of information on sixteenth-century trade hubs and exchanged goods from the Red Sea to the Far East, Tomé Pires provides a wondrous, picturesque, fascinating description of his preferred place, the busy port town of Malacca, with its thriving business activities and the merchants' hustle and bustle:

«No trading port as large as Malacca is known, nor any where they deal in such fine and highly prized merchandise. Goods from all over the East are found here; goods from all over the West are sold here».

[In the original Portuguese text: «Nam se sabe tam grossa escalla como a de malaq nem em que se tratem tam nobres e estimadas mercadarias; aquy se acha Da valia de todo levante aquy se vemde de toda valia De todo ponente»].

Amid the vast amount of practical information contained in this comprehensive work, Tomé Pires could not omit to include a mention of the legendary lore which lived its mysterious life in the very neighborhood of his mercantile workplace, Malacca: the fairy tale of Gunong Ledang.

Of course, Pires only provides a brief reference, from his factual, tradesman-like point of view, to what he considers just a silly legend, of no interest at all for stern, engaged businessmen like he himself was.

Fig. 26 - A description of the port of Malacca from Tomé Pires' *Suma oriental* (manuscript 1248, Bibliothèque de l'Assemblée Nationale de France, Paris, sixteenth century), folium 160r

Nonetheless, his mention is of great significance for our investigation.

For here is what Tomé Pires says of Gunong Ledang and the princess of the mountain:

«They say that opposite to Piraman there is an island where there are only women and they have no men, [...] and that some are made pregnant by the wind. This opinion is held by the people of these parts, in the same way as they do about the enchanted Queen in the mount of Malacca called Gulom Leydam».

[In the original Portuguese text: «Dizem que Defromte de piramã esta huuã Ilha ê que nam ha senom molheres nam tem homenes [...] et que outras

empremha do vento esta opynjam tem os destas partes como no momte de malaqa que se chama gulom leydam a Raynha emcamtada»].

Fig. 27 - Princess of Gunong Ledang from Tomé Pires' *Suma oriental* (manuscript 1248, Bibliothèque de l'Assemblée Nationale de France, Paris, sixteenth century), folium 146r

So, when incidentally describing a different fairy tale on magical women possibly pertaining (according to Armando Cortesão) to the Mentawai Islands, on the western side of Sumatra, Tomé Pires shows that he is well aware of the existence of a similar tale «in the mount of Malacca called Gulom Leydam», in which people used to believe that an «enchanted queen» had her abode.

It is clear that in the mind of Pires all that is only babble and chatter for simpletons. However, in expressing his own disbelief, he includes a totally unexpected remark, a full century before Manuel Godinho de Erédia wrote his own words about sibilline caves and Sibyls:

«People believe in this, as others believe in the Amazons and the Sybil of Rome».

[In the original Portuguese text: «Jaz esta fee no pouo como no pouo outros amazonas et Sebilla de Roma»].

Fig. 28 - The words «gulom leydam» and «sebilla de roma» highlighted from Tomé Pires' *Suma oriental* (manuscript 1248, Bibliothèque de l'Assemblée Nationale de France, Paris, sixteenth century), folium

146r

Once again, the Princess of Gunong Ledang is associated, for comparison reasons, to the lore of Sibyls. Manuel Godinho de Erédia did so in 1613, and we see now that Tomé Pires, too, did the same a hundred years earlier, in 1515.

And something perplexing happens with Pires' mention: he mentions a «Sybil of Rome» (in the original Portuguese text: «sebilla de Roma»).

What sort of Sibyl is this? Let's try to find out in the next chapter.

7. The 'Sibyl of Rome'

7.1 Who was Tomé Pires' Sibyl of Rome?

The problem is that in Rome there were no Sibyls. No one of them, in the classical list stated by Lactantius, nor in the subsequent, additional medieval enumerations, is ever referenced as a Roman Sibyl, or something the like.

Of course, we may cite the Cumaean Sibyl, whose sibilline books, according to an ancient legend also mentioned by Lactantius, were sold to Roman king Tarquinius Priscus and preserved in Rome, at the Temple of Jupiter Capitolinus. However, it was universally known, across the classical, medieval and later literature that that Sibyl was from Cumae, not from Rome.

We may also turn to the Tiburtine Sibyl, whose abode was in Tibur, a location not far from Rome. According to another legend, she provided an interpretation of a same allegorical dream that one hundred Roman senators had dreamt on a same night, with the legend partly developing its tale in Rome. But the Tiburtine Sibyl was no queen nor princess, as her figure seems to refer to a nymph of the waters or a prophesying woman, inhabiting no specific traditional abode and ruling no court.

Thus Sibyls, originating from an ancient Greek oracular tradition, have never resided in classical or medieval Rome.

So what did Tomé Pires mean by saying «Sybil of Rome»?

In the vicinity of Rome, we know only one Sibyl: the Sibyl of the Apennines.

And only the Apennine Sibyl, among all known oracular sibilline figures, was not a mere woman endowed with prophesying faculties. The Apennine Sibyl, only, was marked by the dignity and authority of a queen, and held a court. Just like Queen Putry.

And only the Sibyl of the Apennines, amid all her classical and medieval sisters, lived an eternal life not tainted by the doom of death (apart from the Cumaean, who could not die and was doomed to live forever as a withered, aging old woman). Just like Queen Putry. And just like Morgan le Fay, who of the Apennine Sibyl is the generating, antecedent fairy character.

And only the Apennine Sibyl lived in a cave hidden within a mountain, Mount Sibyl, her abode protected by a cover of magical spells. Just like Gunung Ledang and the fairy court of Queen Putry.

Furthermore, no classical or medieval Sibyls had the ability to transform themselves, as they were just oracular women. But, like Queen Putry, and like Morgan le Fay, the Sibyl of the Apennines could transform herself (as reported by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale).

Finally, the hue of necromancy colors both Queen Putry, with her dead men's bones and requests for cups full of blood, and the Apennine Sibyl, whose ancestor is necromantic enchanter Morgan le Fay, and was compared to Erichtho by twelfth-century poet Hartmann von Aue. Erichtho, who was also compared to Prince Putry in the words written by Manuel Godinho de Erédia.

So, there is matter enough to presume that the «Sybil of Rome», who was mentioned by Tomé Pires in his sixteenth-century *Suma Oriental* as a fairy tale with some analogies with that concerning «the enchanted Queen in the mount of Malacca called Gulom Leydam», might actually be the Apennine Sibyl.

All clues seem to point to Mount Sibyl and the magical queen who lived beneath its cliff.

Yet, a problem seems to thwart our identification attempt.

Our Apennine Sibyl resided in the area of Norcia. Not Rome. She wasn't a «Sybil of Rome».

Can we overcome this specific issue? Let's proceed to the next paragraph and try to address the matter.

7.2 Rome, Norcia and Montemonaco

As we know, the Apennine Sibyl traditionally has her abode within Mount Sibyl, a peak raising in central Italy, between Norcia, in the province of Umbria, and Montemonaco, in the province of Marche.

The two locations, Norcia and Montemonaco, are the nearest settlements to Mount Sibyl, each set on a different side of the Apennine chain: for centuries they have been keeping watch over the magical mountain inhabited by a fairy oracle; for centuries visitors coming from all over Europe have been taking their first steps toward the crowned mount starting from one town or the other; for centuries they have guarded the paths leading to the legendary site, Norcia from the western side and Montemonaco from the eastern.

First of all, how far are we from Rome? Not much, a distance of some seventy miles lies between Norcia and the former capital of an empire, and eighty miles as to Montemonaco.

However, historically the link between the three locations is much closer. Because Norcia and Montemonaco, at the beginning of the sixteenth century, the time of Tomé Pires, both belonged to the Papal States.

Norcia, from which Guerrino the Wretch began its journey to the slopes of Mount Sibyl, was a commune, a partially-independent local entity, governed by wealthy families holding official posts but set under the

control of the Pope, who approved the local charters and appointed some of the magistrates to the main administrative offices. Starting from year 1506, Pope Julius II established an increasingly direct control over the town by sending an executive commissioner from Rome, the first in a row across the following decades, subsequently accompanied by armed soldiers. Then the Papal commissioner became a governor and eventually, in 1569, the Pope established in Norcia a Prefecture of the Mountain for the administration of a large portion of the Apennine area surrounding the town.

Fig. 29 - Rome, Norcia, Montemonaco and Mount Sibyl in Italy

As to Montemonaco, from which Antoine de la Sale ascended Mount Sibyl in 1420, it was a commune, too, partially independent and subject to papal rule as well, through the control of the March of Ancona, a papal province. As Montemonaco and Norcia are located in a same area - Montemonaco on the eastern side of the Sibillini Mountain Range, Norcia on the western - in 1583 the former will be assigned to the Prefecture of the Mountain, whose officials were based in the latter.

This administrative inclusion will last for a few years only. Nonetheless, the links between Montemonaco and Norcia, lying just across the main peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range, were significant. They shared - and often quarreled over - a main mountainous trail which crossed the high

crests of the Sibillini at the peak of Palazzo Borghese (at an elevation of more than 7,000 feet), whose name was 'Imperial Road', an ancient track that connected the eastern and western versants of the Sibillini used by the shepherds with their herds and by many sorts of smugglers, outlaws, bandits and venture soldiers. By the way, the 'Road' just ran between the two sinister, notorious locations: the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

Fig. 30 - The southern area of the Sibillini Mountain Range with Norcia, Montemonaco and the elevated trail which ran between the two settlements

So Norcia and Montemonaco, as seen from the papal institutions in Rome, were virtually - and in some periods also administratively - considered as parts of a same territory: a land through which, in the sixteenth century, brave condottieri with their armed men used to cut through Italy from east to west and back again, in search of castels to win for themselves, ravaging hamlets and killing unarmed peasants. It was also a land treaded by alleged magicians and self-styled necromancers, who headed to Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore; and they certainly were not welcome by the papal authorities.

So it is not a surprise to find, in the papal decree issued by Pope Pius V in 1569 for the establishment of the Prefettura della Montagna, that the new prefect in Norcia would share law enforcement duties with the authority based on the eastern side of the Apennines, with a direct reference to the village of Montemonaco:

«Item we want and we grant to you [the new prefect, editor's note] that in the Castles and Strongholds of Monte Gallo, Monte Monaco and Monte Fortino which are under the rule of our province of the border district of Ancona, and which border the Mountain set under your jurisdiction, you and the Governor of the said province, in the prosecution and punishment of any sort of criminals and outlaws, may proceed together by mutual action, so as to achieve joint prevention».

Fig. 31 - Norcia and law enforcement on the eastern side of the Apennines in the papal decree issued by Pope Pius V in 1569, translation in Italian drawn from Feliciano Patrizi-Forti's *Memorie Storiche di Norcia* (Norcia, 1869), p. 508

[In the Italian translation from the original Latin text: «Inoltre vogliamo e ti concediamo, che nei Castelli e Rocche di Monte Gallo, Monte Monaco e Monte Fortino che sono sotto il governo della Provincia della Marca nostra Anconitana, e che sono limitrofi alla Montagna di tua giurisdizione, tu ed il Governatore della medesima Provincia, nel perseguire e punire ogni sorta di delinquenti ed esuli, possiate procedere cumulativamente, e fra voi abbia luogo la prevenzione»].

The Pope's intention was to establish, in this critical area, a sole jurisdiction to effectively enforce law, having noted that (writes the Pope himself in his decree) «often, owing to different points of view and disagreements among officials, crime is not duly prosecuted» (in the original Latin text: «sepius ob diversitatem ac dissensionem officialium delicta remanent impunita»).

In this sense, Caterina Comino, in her paper *La prefettura della Montagna come esempio di distrettuazione periferica* (in *Archivi per la Storia - Rivista dell'Associazione Nazionale Archivistica Italiana*, 2000, p. 234), points out that the Prefect in Norcia was in charge for the decision of all criminal cases under the Papal States' penal law:

«Jurisdiction over penal cases is in Norcia firmly in the hands of the Prefect, and so of the central power itself. In the criminal cases of greater momentum, i.e. those exceeding a penalty of five years as a galley slave to work at the oar, the Prefect - as in general all papal governors - had to inform the 'Sacra Consulta' and get binding directive from this body [headquartered in Rome, editor's note]»

In the same article, Comino retraces the turbulent story of the area of Norcia, with many famed condottieri and armed bands crossing the area of Norcia, pillaging the villages during the sixteenth century, and outlines the flow of correspondence that this mountainous area between Norcia and Montemonaco, though remote as it was, exchanged with the papal court in Rome (p. 241):

«The attention of Rome to the government of the Prefettura della Montagna is mainly evidenced by the documents sent by the cardinals of the Secretariat of State to the Prefects, which include a wealth of general instructions on the behaviour to be maintained in the countryside as well as in the town, and on the procedures to be applied to the transfer of the

outlaws who were apprehended, to the alerts concerning the passage of armed bands, and further directives on the handling of specific cases».

So in the sixteenth century Norcia, Montemonaco and the Sibillini Mountain Range, all included in the Papal States, were strictly connected to Rome and the Pope, especially on the grounds of law enforcement, crime repression, and control of the circulation of people moving across, to and from the mountainous chain.

But in the sixteenth century Norcia and Montemonaco were also the main gateways if one wanted to address the legendary sites where a sinister Sibyl had her subterranean abode, and a Roman prefect and his demons eerily stirred the waters of lake.

Norcia and Montemonaco, administrated and controlled by Rome, provided the principal access pathways to the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate. Let's illustrate this topic further in the following paragraph.

7.3 Norcia and Montemonaco as the entryways to legend (under Rome's control)

In the sixteenth century, at the time of Tomé Pires, the political, administrative and jurisdictional connections between Rome, Norcia and Montemonaco were strong and patent, as we saw in the previous paragraph.

In addition to that, we also know that Norcia and Montemonaco represented the mutually-alternative starting point (the former from the west, the latter from the east) to initiate the journey up to the crowned peak of Mount Sibyl, where the entrance of a magical cave was to be found.

We must stress the point that the two locations, in the fifteenth century, were already significantly renowned, following the mentions provided by Petrus Berchorius, Fazio degli Uberti, Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale. In 1444 Felix Hemmerlin, in his work *De Nobilitate et Rusticitate Dialogus*, had even established a direct connection between Mount Sibyl and the German Venusberg of the Tannhäuser legend («... not far from the town of Norcia and the castle of Montefortino [a hamlet not far from

Montemonaco, editor's note] lies Mount Sibyl [...] This mount is known as Venusberg...»). And, in the same years, Antoine de la Sale wrote his narrative on Mount Sibyl being urged by Agnes of Burgundy, who owned a tapestry representing Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl, in her palace at Moulins-sur-Allier, the capital of the Duchy of Bourbon in central France.

With their literary works, all of them had just imparted new momentum to a rumour which was already widely spread across Italy and abroad. At that time, everybody in Europe knew about the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

Did Rome effected some kind of control over the access to the two magically-renowned sites, set high up in the mountain and served by the 'Imperial Road' trail?

The answer to our question seems to be in the affirmative: as reported by many literary sources, all dating back to the fifteenth and sixteenth century, nobody was allowed to the magical cave's entryway and the lake's waters lying up amid the crests of Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore, without getting a permission from the local authorities, which seemingly acted on behalf of the Pope in Rome.

In Andrea da Barberino's romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, the valiant knight Guerrino, starting from Norcia and heading to the cliff of Mount Sibyl, must call at a small intermediate post, which is easily identified with Castelluccio, a small mountain settlement actually lying six miles from Norcia, between the said town and Mount Vettore:

«In the early morning, after a full breakfast, they rode their horses towards the stronghold of Sabine: it was six miles from Norcia. When they got to the stronghold they reported to an officer of the castle: he began to threaten The Wretch by saying that he was a hopeless man, and those who went to that place underwent a formal censure by the Church...».

[In the original Italian text: «et alquanto fata collatione a bonhora montono a cavallo et inverso la roca de la Sabina cavalcono: la quale era appresso a Norza a vi miglia. E zonti a questa rocha funo apresentata a uno ufficiale del castelo: el quale comenzo a menazare el Meschino dicendo como lui era desperato, e che lo era scomunicato colui che andava in quello loco...»].

parechiati doi boni ronzini: et alquanto fata collatione a bonho
 ra montono a caualo et inuerfo la roca de la Sabina caualcono: la quale
 era apresso a Norza a vi. miglia. E zonti a questa rocha funo apresentati
 a uno officiale del castelo: el quale comēzo a menazare el Meschino dicē
 do como lui era desperato, e chelo era scomunicato colui che andaua in
 quello loco: e tuto faccuā quello rectore p torli quella andata dicendo a
 .G. uui me parete psona da bene e uolete adare doue nō uano altro che ri
 baldi o gente despata. E tu mescre Anuelo nō te uergognitu de cōsiliarlo

Fig. 32 - The trail to Mount Sibyl guarded by an officer from Norcia, from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Venice, 1480), folia 96 and 97

And in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, Antoine de la Sale informs the reader that a formal clearance was to be granted by the local authorities in Norcia if one intended to ascend Mount Vettore and get to the Lake of Pilate, which faces Mount Sibyl across a glacial valley:

traide y trouuent aucun Il est mal venu Et
 nauoit pas souz temps qui y fut pris deus
 hommes dont l'un estoit prestre ce prestre fut
 admené a la dite cite de norce & la fut martire
 & aué. **L**autre fut taillé a piéces & puis loute
 dedens le lac par ceulz qui les auoient pris
Mais si aucun prenoit plaisir a veoir ce
 dit lac pour l'assuete de sa personne lui con
 uient aller au seigneur de la dite cite qui
 voulentiers lui donneront conduit pour ce veoir
 sans autre chose faire sil veut en estat donne
 de bien

Fig. 33 - Norcia and the clearance provided by the local authorities to visit the lake of Pilate from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 5r)

«And not much time has elapsed since two men were caught, one of them being a priest. The priest was brought to the said town of Norcia and there was martyred and burnt. [...] Yet if anybody wants to enjoy the view of this lake, for his own safety it is better for him to go to the lords of the said town, and they will gladly assign to him a guide to pay the visit, but just it and nothing else, provided that he goes as a well-intentioned man».

[In the original French text: «Et navoit pas long temps quel y fut prins deux hommes dont lun estoit prestre ce preste fut admene a la dicte cite de norce et la fut martire et ars. [...] Mais se aucun prenoit plaisir a veoir ce dit lac pour la sseuret de sa personne lui convient aler aux seugneurs de la ditte cite qui volentiers lui donneront conduit pour ce veoir, sans autre chose faire, sil vait en estat domme de bien»].

Even Arnold von Harff, a German knight who in the years 1496-1499 carried out a journey across many countries, visited the renowned Cave and the eerie Lake accompanied by a papal official from Norcia or Castelluccio:

«Item we travelled [...] to a little town called Norde [corrupted for 'Norcia', editor's note], and close to this is Lady Venus' mountain [a reference to the German legend of Tannhuser, closely linked to the Apennine Sibyl, editor's note]. At the end of this mountain is a castle in which lives a castellan of the Pope, whom with great good fortune we found in the town. I made him aware of what I had heard and told him in Latin that we had a mind to visit Lady Venus' mountain, since in our country many wonders were reported of it. [...] Early next morning he rode with us to the mountain in which many caves have been hewn [...]. I went with him into the caves, but could not creep into some of them for many were fallen in, but others stood open».

[In the original German text: «Item [...] tzogen wir zo eynem kleynen steetgen heyscht Norde. Haert dae by licht vrou Venus berch, an wylchen berch an deme eynde licht eyn berch sloess, daes off woent eyn casteleyn des pays, dem wir zo allen geluck in desem steetgen vonden. Ich maicht balde kuntschaff mit yeme ind saicht yem in latine, wie wir dae in der meynonge weren den berch vrou Venus zo besiene, as man uns in unsen landen vil wonders dae van sechte. [...] Des morgens vro reyt he mit uns an den berch, daer inne stund vil locher gehauwen [...] Ich geynck mit yeme in

die locher. Ich koent dae anders nyet zo sien krijgen, dan etzliche locher waeren zo gevallen ind etzliche stunden noch offen»].

Item van desern steetgen Arieet tzogen wir zo eynem
40 kleynen steetgen heyscht Norde. haert dae by licht vrou

38

Venus berch, an wylchen berch an deme eynde licht eyn
berch sloess, daer off woent eyn casteleyn des pays, dem
wir zo allen geluck in desern steetgen vonden. ich maicht
balde kuntschaff mit yeme ind saicht yem in latine, wie wir
5 dae in der meynonge weren den berch vrou Venus zo be-
siene, as man vns in vnser landen vil wonders dae van
sechte. der casteleyn waert mich an lachen ind dedes vnss
des auontz gar gude geselschaff. des morgens vro reyrt he
mit vns an den berch. daer inne stund vil locher gehauwen,
10 as vnder Valckenberch ader vnder Triecht, dae man vss
dat steetgen ind dat slos gebouwet hait. ich geynck mit
yeme in die locher. ich koent dae anders nyet zo sien krij-
gen, dan etzliche locher waeren zo geuallen ind etzliche
stunden noch offen. Item wir tzogen myt dem casteleyne

Fig. 34 - The excerpt on the visit to Mount Sibyl from a printed edition of *Die Pilgerfahrt des Ritters Arnold von Harff* edited by E. Von Groote (Cologne, 1860)

Even more assertive is Father Fortunato Ciucci, who in his *Chronicles of the antique town of Norsia*, dating to 1653, writes the following words concerning «The Sibyl's Cave and its wonders» (in Italian: «Della Grotta della Sibilla e delle sua Maraviglie»):

«Because of all that and with a view to keeping the mountain unblemished from any mischief, the Castel of Mount Precino [ancient name of Castelluccio di Norcia, editor's note] was built in this very spot, because of all that the tower of the Knights was raised near the mountain pass, where all summer guards were maintained with a good number of Soldiers».

[In the original Italian text: «Per questo e per mantener netta la montagna da ogni Latrocinio fu fabricato il Castel Monte Pricino in questo luogo, per questo fu alzata la torre de' Cavalieri vicino al passo, dove per tutta l'Estate vi si faceva la guardia con buon numero de Soldati»].

And we must also remember the two earlier mentions, both dating back to the fourteenth century, of a careful, vigilant surveillance held at the Lake of Pilate by the local authorities. The first mention is provided, in his

Reductorium Morale, by Petrus Berchorius, who got the information from a prominent cleric, possibly a bishop:

«I heard a remarkable, horrific tale about Norcia, the Italian town, that was reported to me as an absolutely proven truth by a certain prelate, a trustworthy person indeed among all men. [...] Today, no men but necromancers can get to the lake withouth being killed by the demons. Because of that, walls were built around the shore of the lake, and watched over by guards, lest necromancers be allowed to access the place to consecrate their books to the demons».

Fig. 35 - The excerpt on the Lake of Norcia taken from the *Reductorium Morale* by Petrus Berchorius (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786), folium 301v

[In the original Latin text: «Exemplum terribile esse circa Norciam Italie civitatem audiui pro vero et pro centies experto narrari a quodam prelato summe inter alios fide digno. [...] ad quem nullus hodie praeter necromanticos potest accedere, quin a daemonibus occidat. Igitur circa terminos lacus facti sunt muri qui a custodibus servantur, ne necromantici pro liberis suis consecrandis daemonibus illuc accedere permittantur»].

The second fourteenth-century mention is retrieved in the *Dittamondo*, a poem written between 1350 and 1367 by Fazio degli Uberti, a poet from Tuscany:

«I don't want to overlook the renown of the Mount of Pilate, where a lake is - which in summers is carefully guarded by watches on duty - because here Simon the Sorcerer ascends to consecrate his spellbook...».

Fig. 36 - The opening folium of Fazio degli Uberti's *Dittamondo* and the verses on the Lake of Pilate from a manuscript dating to 1447 (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Italien 81, folia 1r and 94v)

[In the original Italian text: «la fama qui non vo' rimagna nuda - del monte di pillato, dov'è il lago - che si guarda l'estate a muda a muda - però che qua s'intende in Simon mago - per sagrar il suo libro in su monta...»].

So, at least according to a number of literary sources, local authorities, especially from the side of Norcia, appear to have exerted their influence and enforced their authority over the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave, maintaining a strict control over the accessibility of the two sites.

Does any official documentation concerning this sort of control exist in the historical archives of Rome, Norcia and Montemonaco? Actually a specific document exists: it dates back to the fifteenth century and was found in Montemonaco, at the foot of Mount Sibyl, as we will see in the next paragraph.

7.4 An official document: prosecution of necromancers in Montemonaco

The references we reported in the previous paragraph, which concern a controlled access to the legendary sites set amid the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range, all come from literary sources.

But what about official orders, decrees and jurisdictional acts concerning the same topic? Can we retrieve any formal statement, dating back to the fifteenth century, about a controlled access to the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate?

We must highlight the point that, at least to our knowledge, no official documentation preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library or the Vatican Apostolic Archive seems to report on such matter, nor any hint to this surveillance has ever been retrieved at the Historical Municipal Archive of Norcia, the Diocesan Archive of Norcia and the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (with one significant exception for the latter - as we will see later in this same paragraph).

So it seems we are not able to retrieve an official confirmation of what literature suggests.

If we turn to Norcia, apparently no documentation on Mount Sibyl is present in the historical archives preserved there (both municipal and diocesan), though perhaps specific research should be conducted on the issue.

For instance, if we look at the Charters of Norcia, dating to the fourteenth century and printed in 1526, we only find in Book V a mention of the Lake (and none about the Sibyl), aimed at defining a formal regulation of its use for cattle watering: shepherds were allowed to bring their animals «to water or bath to the lake set in the Mount of Vettore» (in the original Italian text: «fosse menato ad bere o ad bagniare allo laco posto nello Monte de Vettore»), without paying any fee provided that they get there and go back in a same day («dasse et tornasse in uno dì»).

A further, potential reference to the Sibyl in the Charters as provided by Father Fortunato Ciucci in his *Chronicles of the antique town of Norsia* (1653), in which the seventeenth-century monk reports that in «paragraph

no. 2 of Book VI of the Charters of Norcia» a mention of the Sibyl's Cave is present, cannot be validated by the contemporary scholar as the perusal of that specific excerpt of the Charters provides no actual confirmation of the presence of the alleged text on the Sibyl as referred by Ciucci.

All that said, when we turn to Montemonaco the investigation proves to be much more fruitful: an official document exists which attests to the attention and worried concern with which the Papal States, since the fifteenth century, looked at what was going on up there, where the high peaks embraced the Lake of Pilate, the Sibyl's Cave and their gloomy mysteries.

Fig. 37 - A mention of the lake of Mount Vettore as it appears in the *Statutorum Nursie* (Perugia, 1526), Book V, Chapter LIV, folium 41

The manuscript was found by the researchers of Progetto Elissa at the Historical Municipal Archive of Montemonaco at the end of the 1990s. Dated June, 15 1452, it was written by a notary public, Vittorino of Ser Ascensio of Santa Vittoria, and contains the acquittal of a number of defendants, a sentence rendered by Cristoforo de Guardarijs, a judge residing in Tolentino (a town of the region of Marche) and dealing with

«spiritual cases» («in spiritualibus» in Latin) at the papal tribunal of the March of Ancona.

Of this manuscript we will talk in more detail in a next paper. In the present article we are interested in noting that the defendants are the local authorities of Montemonaco and the inhabitants of the same hamlet («... priorum universitatem communis et homines terra Montis Monaci...») who «during the months of July, August and September of the said year accommodated and housed in the commune and provided support, advice and help to each and all of them [...] to exercise alchemy and willing to consecrate some evil and fiendish books at the lake of the Sibyl, with the will and intention to follow the fiendish art, and continue with their art in scorn of Divine Majesty and endangering the Christian faith to the damage and disdain of the souls of many Christians».

[In the original Latin text: «... mensibus julii, augusti et settembris ditti anni [...] retinuerunt et receptaverunt in comunis ac ipsis er cuilibet ipsorum prestiterunt ausilium, consilium et favorem [...] in fatiando archimiam et volendo sacrare libros nonnullos malignos et diabolicos ad lacum Sibille animo et intentione sequendi artem diabolicam et in eorum arte continuandi ignominiam divine Maiestatis et in preiuditium fidei christiane et dapnum et vilipendium nonnullarum animarum fidelium»].

So people from abroad used to come to Montemonaco and ascend to the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave to perform magical rituals; in this circumstances, Montemonaco was charged with providing forbidden help and assistance to those ill-intentioned visitors. One of the visitors, «Angelus de Adversa», an 'alchemist' coming from the Kingdom of Naples, was even taken and imprisoned.

Prosecution was initiated and managed by the papal authorities of the March of Ancona in Tolentino, and the sentence was rendered «in the name of our most holy Father in Christ and our lord, out of the divine providence, pope N[icholas] V, and in the name of the Holy Church of Rome and the reverend in Christ father and lord B[artholomew] Archbishop of Ravenna» (in the original Latin text: «pro sanctissimo in Christo patre et domino nostro N[icolao] divina providentia pape V et pro sancta romana ecclesia et pro reverendo in Christo patre domino B[artholomeo] Archiepiscopo Ravenne»).

Fig. 38 - The acquittal of the commune of Montemonaco dated June, 15 1452 (manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco, from *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.*, transcribed and translated by Mons. Giuseppe Ghilarducci, Montemonaco, 1998)

This manuscript is of utmost importance as it certifies that the Papal States, in the name of the Pope and through their jurisdictional branch in the province of the March of Ancona and the local authorities in Montemonaco, intended to maintain a strict control over the forbidden

activities that ill-intentioned people wished to carry out within the crests of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

This is the proof that the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate were attentively scrutinised from Rome. And that the Pope didn't want those sites to work as a focal point for magicians, necromancers, wizards and heretics.

The eye of Rome was on Norcia and Montemonaco. And, most probably, still is today.

7.5 A Sibyl of the Apennines under discrete papal surveillance across the centuries

As shown in the previous paragraph, it appears that the renowned, legendary oracle sitting on a mountain between Norcia and Montemonaco - a most famous Sibyl at the time of Tomé Pires, as attested during the fifteenth and sixteenth century by a plethora of literary mentions circulating all around Europe - was duly kept under surveillance by the local officials, subject to papal rule. And it appears that this careful watch was maintained on behalf of the central authority: the Pope in Rome.

But why should the Papal States have kept a suspicious eye on such a legendary tale, a fairy narrative apparently good for peasants, shepherds and simpletons only?

As we saw in the previous paragraphs, the fact was that this fairy tale used to attract a multitude of unwanted, ill-intentioned visitors, who often travelled to the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate with a view to performing some sort of magical rituals or undergo some fairy-like experience, be it the summoning of demons, the consecration of spellbooks, or the visit to an enchanted court where an unchaste life could be lived forever, at least until the Judgement Day, as we have also illustrated in the series of articles *The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend*.

All this was to be restrained and inhibited, as Leandro Alberti, a dominican friar who wrote a renowned historical and geographical work, the *General description of Italy*, expressed in 1550: «... that most famous Lake of which

tales are told about the conjuring of devils summoned by sorcerers, who would speak to them. If such accounts were true, it would certainly deserve severe condemnation, and such witchcrafts should be hardly punished under both Canonical and Imperial laws: I believe those are but fairy tales and lies, as I will show later in my book when describing the Sibyl's Cave» [in the original Italian text: ... quel tanto famoso Lago de'l quale se dice che vi appaiono i demoni costretti dagli incantatori, & che qui vi parlano con essi. Che se così fusse sarebbe cosa molto biasimevole, & tali incantamenti meriterebbero gravissime punctioni secondo le leggi Canoniche & Imperiali: Io credo che siano tutte favole e menzogne, come poi dimostrerò descrivendo la Grotta della Sibilla»].

Because the Church did not intend to let malevolent people «follow the fiendish art, and continue with their art in scorn of Divine Majesty [...] endangering the Christian faith to the damage and disdain of the souls of many Christians», as effectively reported in the manuscript found in Montemonaco,

So it appears that some kind of discreet vigilance was kept over the Sibillini Mountain Range. But it was not only a matter of mere vigilance, of circumspect surveillance from Rome: it was also the management of direct action, as it seems to come into view from some of the literary sources we have been perusing across this series of articles, and even in this very paper.

Some of those sources report about a conclusive, or possibly repeated, activity carried out by the Pope or Popes to irrevocably shut the entryway to the Sibyl's Cave, so as to prevent anybody from accessing the supposed magical realm of the oracular prophetess.

«[The knight] went to Pope Innocent in the year 1352, while others say that it was Pope Urban said Grimoard in the year 1362, and others also say that it was Pope Urban from Limousin in the year 1377. This Pope excommunicated all who went or had visited the cave and refused to impart his absolution. The same Pope had the pathway to the Lake [of Pilate] broken, out of the necromancers who persisted in visiting the place, and had the track up across the crown of Mount Sibyl demolished, lest nobody may still climb, and had the cave's entrance filled up».

[In the original French text: «Si vint au pape Innocent de l'an mil IIIc LII, autres disans que ce fut au pape Urbain, dit Grimouault de l'an mil III LXII et disent encores que fut le pape Urbain de Limozin de l'an mil III LXXVII. Cestui escommunia tous ceuls qui aloient et qui avoient este et retenoit a lui labsolution. Lequel fist tailler la chaussee du dit lac pour les nigromans qui tant y aloient et fist rompre le pas de la couronne du mont de la Sibille afin que nul ny peust monter, et combler lentre»].

Fig. 39 - The Pope forbids entrance to the Sibyl's Cave from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 17v)

«The Pope immediately ordered that the entryway to that cave be dismantled lest nobody could ever enter again, and with formal decrees stated that ingress to the cave was forbidden forever».

[In the original French text: «Le pape manda incontinant desrompre lentre de celle cave et empescher que jamais homme ny peust retourner et deffendre par grans esdiz que nul jamais plus ny entrast»].

Fig. 40 - The Pope forbids entrance to the Sibyl's Cave from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 20v)

And in a later mention, which is retrieved in an edition of Ptolemy's *Geography* compiled by Antonio Giovanni Magini, an Italian scientist and geographer, in year 1617, we find the following:

«In the Apennines there is a huge and frightful cavern which people calls the Sibyl's cave, of which many fairy tales are told by liars and cheaters, according to which, as once many sorcerers and wicked men were frequently seen by the inhabitants of Norcia gathering there, they were forced to seal that Sibyl's cave or cavern; and in addition to that they set watchful guards at the lake».

Fig. 41 - The excerpt on the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Norcia from Antonio Giovanni Magini's *Ptolemy's Geography* (Arnhem, 1617)

[In the original Latin text: «In Appennino immane horribileque antrum, quod Sybillae caverna vulgo dicitur, de qua multa fabulosa à mendacibus, ac impostoribus recitantur; quamobrem cum Nursini frequentem olim Magorum et maleficorum hominum numerum ad haec loca continuo concurrere conspexissent, speculam seu cavernam illam Sybillinam operire conacti fuerunt, ac praetera custodes ad lacum circumspectos ponere»].

G V E R R I N O
D E T T O I L
M E S C H I N O,

*Nuovamente ristampato, & rivisto, e
dalla Santa Inquisitione Coretto.*

Di maniera, che in ogni sua parte e fatto
chiaro, & illustre.

chi non ha cercato del mondo, non è homo. Disse
G. vdisti mai dir della Incantatrice Alcina, l'hostier
disse, ch'era in certe montagne li appresso, ma liti
non esserui andato, nè hauer voglia di andarui e
se voi haueffi voglia di andarui, per Dio cacciate

vdendoli ragionar comincio a dir de gli fatti delli
incantamenti, e parládo di vna cosa e di vn'altra
vn di loro disse a gli altri, di questa città ho vdito
dir, che ci è la Incantatrice Alcina, laqual s'ingano
no di modo, che ella credea che Dio scendeisse in
lei, quando incarno in Maria vergine, e per questo
ella ti dispero, e fu giudicata per questa cagion in
queste montagne. Disse il M. e questo chi lo puo

IN VENETIA, M. D. LXXXIX.

Pressò Gio. Battista L'insadino.

Fig. 42 - The edition of Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* printed in Venice in 1589, with the replacement of «Sibyl» with «Alcina»

In the subsequent centuries, the papal attentive scrutiny of all that might concern the Apennine Sibyl and the unwanted diffusion of her dark renown led to a stricter control of the published editions of Andrea da Barberino's romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, which were experiencing a wide success amid readers and listeners of all social conditions. With the edition issued in Venice in 1589, «newly reprinted and reviewed and amended by the Holy Inquisition» (in Italian: «nuovamente ristampato et rivisto et dalla Santa Inquisitione coretto»), as threateningly reported on the opening page,

those readers were given a modified novel, in which no Sibyl appeared anymore, as she was everywhere replaced by «Alcina the enchanter» (in Italian: «la incantatrice Alcina»), a reference to the literary, harmless character staged by Ludovico Ariosto in his *Orlando furioso*, an innocuous enchanter who had no caves to be visited in real life.

This sort of discrete papal surveillance, apparently maintained by the Church across the centuries, seems to have left some faint traces even in our contemporary age, as we highlighted in our previous paper *Four years from the Chthonian legend* (2024). In a speech delivered in 2017 by H.E. Renato Boccardo, Archbishop of the ecclesiastic district of Spoleto - Norcia, the prelate pronounced the following significant words:

«Our archdiocese extends in the very heart of Apennines, across a territory which in antiquity stretched out far beyond the present borders, as it reached as far as Marche and Abruzzo. A hard, harsh land, commanded by the mountains of the Sibyl...».

La nostra Archidiocesi si estende nel cuore dell'Appennino, in un territorio che anticamente andava ben oltre i confini attuali, raggiungendo le Marche e l'Abruzzo. Un territorio difficile, aspro, dominato dai monti della Sibilla, che sorprende il viandante dopo ogni curva con piani ondulati e dolcissimi, come quelli di Castelluccio o di Colfiorito. Un territorio che ha una fisionomia artistica particolare come il suo paesaggio, anzi ad esso strettamente legata, il risultato unico e irripetibile

Fig. 43 - H.E. Renato Boccardo's remarks on the Sibyl, from *La bellezza ferita*, in *XIX Pastoral Workshop Pilgrimage: Faith and Beauty* (Rome, 2017), p. 3

[In the original Italian text: «La nostra Archidiocesi si estende nel cuore dell'Appennino, in un territorio che anticamente andava ben oltre i confini

attuali, raggiungendo le Marche e l'Abruzzo. Un territorio difficile, aspro, dominato dai monti della Sibilla...»].

As we wrote in *Four years from the Chthonian legend*, «the Catholic Church is always there, on the alert. A centuries-old confrontation, which still goes on though in a low tone. Even in our present epoch of Internet, smartphones and artificial intelligence».

Rome and the Apennine Sibyl are always been in close contact. And still they are.

7.6 Further literary links between the Apennine Sibyl, Rome and the Pope

There are also other significant occurrences which hint to a close link that seems to exist between the Sibyl of the Apennines and the ancient, illustrious town from where the Pope rules the Church: Rome.

In all the major literary traditions concerning Mount Sibyl and dating back to the fifteenth century - the romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, Antoine de la Sale's *The paradise of Queen Sibyl*, the German lore on Tannhäuser - the Sibyl's Cave and the Pope are directly connected.

In fact, the characters staged in all the listed literary sources, after their sinful visit to the hidden realm of the lusty fairy queen, and in the wake of their subsequent repentance, they all head for Rome to ask for papal forgiveness: a journey that apparently is not so troublesome, as it is always presented as straight and direct.

In Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* the main character Guerrino, immediately after his escape from the enchanted Sibyl's Cave, rides to Rome, with a trip of a few days, in search of the papal pardon:

«He journeyed for many days heading to Rome. At the hotel he rested one day: then he went to St. Peter, and asked many people to have the chance to talk to the Holy Father [...] He kneeled down to the Pope's feet, he kissed them while he wept, as he cried for forgiveness». [in the original Italian text: «per molte giornate andò a Roma. A lo albergo se reposò uno giorno:

poi andò a santo Pietro, e domandò a molti de parlare a lo santo padre [...] inzinchiose in sina a li soi piedi, e basò li piedi sempre pianzendo, e cridando misericordia»].

Capitolo. clvii.
 Ornato fino a lo castello dito Sibina: la fera albergono li: e laltro di uenèo a norza & albergo cō Anuelo: doue el Melchio ste te tre zorni & rendete molte gratie ad Anuelo e monto a caua lo armato de le sue arme. Lo oro e larzento lasso ad Anuelo: e scarfamē te porto tanti denari che lo conduceffe a roma: e recomandose a dio. E partito da Norza: per molte giornate ando a Roma. A lo albergo se re pofo uno giorno: poi ando a santo P ietro: e domando a molti de parla re a lo santo padre. Ogni homo se ne rideua: & alcuni domandaua dena

tori. el portonaro non lo uoleua lassare intrare in quella altra sala: ma lui spinse piu forte de loro: & intro dentro: e comenzo a cridare miseri cordia. el santo padre udendo cridare: li fece dire che lui se faceffe auanti: inzinchiose in fina a li soi piedi: e baso li piedi sempre pianzendo: e cridando misericordia. & disse santissimo padre in terra habi misericordia de mi che io ho tanto fallato cōtra dio: che in terra nō e mazior pec

Fig. 44 - From Mount Sibyl to Rome, from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Venice, 1480), Chapter CLVII

The same visit to the Pope in Rome is made by the German knight depicted by Antoine de la Sale in his *Paradise*:

«And when chance occurred that they went out of the cave, the way we recounted, they went down the mountain and headed towards Rome as soon as they could. [...] When they got to Rome, with no further delay, they rushed to the church of St. Peter. Then he threw himself to the feet of a priest [...] Holy Father, said the knight [...] I come to you, the Vicar of God, to beg for forgiveness and mercy».

[in the original French text: «Et quant adventure les ot mis hors de la cave par la maniere quil est dit, descendirent jus du mont et alerent le plus brief quilz peuvent a Rome. [...] Et quant il fut à Romme, sans plus actendre, se frappa en l'eglise Saint Pierre. Lors se getta es piez d'ung penancier [...] Pere Saint, dist le chevalier [...] je viens à vous, Vicaire de Dieu, pour vous requerir pardon et mercy»].

Fig. 45 - From Mount Sibyl to Rome, from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 17r)

And another trip to Rome is carried out by Tannhäuser following his stay in the Venusberg:

«He leaveth now the mountain.
 "I'll set my trust upon the pope,
 I'll go to mercy's fountain.
 [...] A pope by name Urban I'll pray
 To see if he'll receive me.
 "O father, holy master mine,
 My sin I would confess thee...»

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TANNHÄUSER
AND THE
MOUNTAIN OF VENUS

A STUDY IN THE LEGEND
OF THE GERMANIC PARADISE

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Right sad of heart and full con-
trite
He leaveth now the mountain.
" I'll set my trust upon the pope,
I'll go to mercy's fountain.

Now merrily I go my way,
Sure God will never leave me!
A pope by name Urban I'll pray,
To see if he'll receive me.

" O father, holy master mine,
My sin I would confess thee
Which I have sinned within my
time;
Forgive it now and bless me!

Fig. 46 - A version of the *Tannhäuserlied* referenced by Philip Stephan Barto in his *Tannhäuser and the Mountain of Venus - A study in the legend of the germanic paradise* (New York, 1916), p. 90

Mount Sibyl, the Sibyl; and their German versions, the Venusberg and Venus. All literary characters connected to them pay their visit to Rome, not only as a token of their desperate longing for an authoritative remission of their sins, but also, and to all appearances, because they weren't very far from the papal city.

According to the various literary sources concerning our legend, Mount Sibyl and Rome seem to be in close connection with one another, as if the former fell within the influence and rule of the latter. As it actually was, in the real world, from a historical and political point of view.

A mutual link which appears to further contribute to our initial assumption: the Apennine Sibyl, when seen from the outside, can easily be seen as a

sort of 'Sibyl of Rome'. And as such Tomé Pires might have mentioned this legend in his sixteenth-century *Suma Oriental*.

8. Conclusive remarks

8.1 a Sibyl from the Apennines to Malacca

After the long journey we made in the present paper across places, centuries and literary sources, we can now try to summarize our findings, check the conjecture we envisaged and evaluate the outcomes of our research, going from Malacca to the Apennines, and back again.

As we illustrated in the previous paragraphs, an old, illustrious Malaysian folktale narrates of beautiful Queen Putry and her enchanted mountain raising near the Malacca, Gunung Ledang. A tale that is made up by narrative building blocks which are somewhat similar to those making up the ancient legend of a Sibyl of the Apennines, whose abode is hidden within Mount Sibyl, central Italy.

The listed similarities do not imply any specific correlation or mutual lineage between the two legends, as they are probably marked only by a mere resemblance which originates from common themes and literary topics just spread all over the world, across different ages and cultures (but some further observation might point to an utterly opposite direction - as you will be able to read at the very end of this paragraph).

Nonetheless, the two legendary tales, both traceable across the sixteenth and seventeenth century, are truly similar; and, possibly, this affinity was noted, in the past, by two different Portuguese authors: Manuel Godinho de Erédia, in 1613; and, a century earlier, in 1515, by Tomé Pires.

De Erédia, a cartographer and military engineer born in Malacca, wrote in his seventeenth-century *Declaração de Malaca e India Meridional com Cathay* that the Malaysian legend of Queen Putry «must be a fairy-tale: but the natives regard it as true. For they assert that on the mountain of Gunoledam there is a certain cavern, like those Pythian and Sibyls' caves,

where the wild Banuas learn the magic arts, and hold communication with the devil in the dark caverns» (in the original Portuguese text: «... como Aquellas cavas Pitias e Sebillas...»).

Can the « cavas [...] Sebillas» mentioned by de Erédia be the Sibyl's Cave of our Apennine legend (which he surely knew owing to his comprehensive education and deep interest in geographic atlases)?

We saw that the only magical Sibyl featuring a cave and a queenly role, similar to Queen Putry, is the Apennine Sibyl; and no other.

But is this enough to settle the matter and state for sure that Manuel Godinho de Erédia's mention refers to Mount Sibyl in Italy? Unfortunately not.

Interestingly enough, a further literary source provides us with a second valuable mention which is absolutely worth taking into consideration: the one retrieved from *Suma oriental* by Tomé Pires, dating back to the sixteenth century.

Fig. 47 - Gunung Ledang, Malaysia

Pires, an apothecary, manager and ambassador, wrote a short sentence on Queen Putry and her legend, reporting that «people believe in this, as others believe in the Amazons and the Sybil of Rome».

Again, just like in de Erédia's excerpt, Queen Putry is found similar to a sybil. Namely, in this case, to a «Sybil of Rome».

Actually, there is no such thing as a 'Sibyl of Rome'. However, the particular affinities which can be retrieved between the tale of Queen Putry and the legend of the Apennine Sibyl seem to steer our investigation towards the latter, even though certainly the Apennines are not Rome.

Why do we think so? Because there has always been a close connection between Mount Sibyl, with its enchanted dweller, and Rome, with its Popes.

As we illustrated in the previous paragraphs, Mount Sibyl was historically placed under the political and administrative authority of the Papal States. Norcia and Montemonaco, the two settlements that provided the ultimate access to the remote, mountainous region where the Sibyl resided, reported to the Pope, and during the sixteenth century were both included in a special province named Prefettura della Montagna. A close control was maintained by the central institutions in Rome as to law enforcement and the administration of justice, in a region trodden by venture soldiers, smugglers, bandits and - an additional concern - alleged sorcerers and necromancers with a penchant for carrying out forbidden magical rituals at the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

Rome, through the local authorities in Norcia and Montemonaco, held a discrete control over the passage of unwanted visitors to the magical cavern. At some times, especially in summers, soldiers were stationed at highland posts, like Castelluccio di Norcia, to prevent any malevolent access to the two famous sites, which were widely known across Europe. And sometimes the papal courts held and tried those visitors, as it happened in 1452 in Montemonaco. Many authors also report that the cave's entrance was sealed by order of the Pope in Rome in an attempt to completely inhibit any visit to the site.

And the main literary sources concerning the legendary tradition of the Apennine Sibyl seem to confirm the special relation which existed between Mount Sibyl and Rome, with many penitent knights walking or riding with their horses straight to the city of the Popes after leaving the magical subterranean abode, with a view to ask for pardon and remission of their abominable, lascivious sins.

So could Tomé Pires have mentioned the «Sybil of Rome», having in his mind the Apennine Sibyl?

We deem that the answer may be in the positive.

The Apennine is not Rome, as we said earlier in this paragraph. Nonetheless, this Sibyl has a specific, historical connection with the Church in Rome. And, as such, may possibly be considered, by an inattentive onlooker, as a plain 'Sibyl of Rome'.

Was Tomé Pires an inattentive onlooker? We can confidently say that he was.

Tomé Pires was an apothecary, an expert of spices and spice trade, a fine connoisseur of trade routes, and trading ports and goods' markets. He was a solid, practical man. He did not care in the least about legends, legendary mountains and legendary queens, and he clearly expressed his view in the few words he wrote on the Malay legend: «... this opinion [on another legendar tale, editor's note] is held by the people of these parts, in the same way as they do about the enchanted Queen in the mount of Malacca called Gulom Leydam. People believe in this, as others believe in the Amazons and the Sybil of Rome».

Silly tales. For simpletons. Meaningless legends with no grounds in real life. Real life that is made, instead, of tangible, lucrative trade. Who would ever believe in, or dedicate his valuable time to, the Queen of Gulom Leydam, the Amazons, or the Sibyl of Rome?

Most probably, Tomé Pires, at the beginning of the sixteenth century, had had the chance to hear about the legend of Mount Sibyl, in Italy. Possibly, he heard about this stupid tale when he was still in Portugal. But who cared about that? It was a topic of no interest to him. Maybe he read somewhere,

or happened to listen, that an Italian fairy tale narrated of a magical Sibyl living in the Apennines, somewhere not far from Rome or connected to Rome in some strange, totally uninteresting way.

All that was just utterly boring to him. So when he stumbled upon some laughable legend from Sumatra, namely the one according to which «women [...who] have no men, [...] and [...] are made pregnant by the wind», he just included a mention of it in his *Suma oriental* by comparing that tale to another foolish story he happened to know, the one on a «Sibyl of Rome», or something the like. A few incidental lines only, by the way. Just before proceeding to topics that were far more interesting to him, such as «the kingdom of Singkel» (in northwest Sumatra), where «benzoin, silk, some pepper, a little gold» can be found - but, beware! «they say that throughout the kingdom they eat men who are enemies», so, dear reader, be careful and stay on the lookout.

Don't ask Tomé Pires to accurately report on the Apennine Sibyl. It is not his work nor mission. But, most probably, even if he did not care, the legend of Mount Sibyl had reached his ears. And, somehow, parenthetically, he brought the legend with him, during his sixteenth-century stay in Malacca. And deposited, unwillingly and unconcerningly, the legendary tale of the Apennine Sibyl in that far away country of the world.

A century later, his words were collected and relayed by Manuel Godinho de Erédia, who, most probably bearing the same Sibyl in mind, compared Queen Putry and Gunung Ledang to the «Sibyls' caves»: the cave of a sibilline princess, in Italy.

Thus, a fascinating travel has taken place from Italy to Malaysia; from the towns of Norcia and Montemonaco to Malacca; from Mount Sibyl to Gunung Ledang. And from the Apennine Sibyl to Queen Putry.

Two legends featuring similar enchantresses and enchanted mountains, calling each other from a distance of more than 6,000 miles. With no specific mutual lineage, but able to bring to the mind of men their dual charming tales, when one or the other is mentioned.

The Sibyl of the Apennines in East Indies, in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. An incredible journey: a journey we tried to retrace by perusing

the words written by Manuel Godinho de Erédia and Tomé Pires. Two very different men: a passionate lover of geography and classical myths, born in Malacca, the former, who dedicated a full chapter to the legend of Queen Putry; and a dependable professional, the latter, who wrote a few words only on a 'Sibyl of Rome', and yet experienced, though only partly and sideways, the astounding mythical power featured by the Apennine Sibyl. So powerful as to reach across the Indian Ocean.

Fig. 48 - Mount Sibyl, Italy

8.2 A suggestion for further research: geom mythology and earthquakes in the legend of Gunung Ledang

Mount Sibyl and Gunung Ledang: two legends that, we said, are totally independent from one another (at least at a first-sight surmise).

Yet, their fascination appears to be so strong that we would like to launch, with the final remarks contained in this paper, the suggestion for a new potential area of investigation, to be possibly searched by our fellow-researchers in Malaysia.

We know from our conjecture as stated in our previous paper *The chthonian legend*, that the Apennine Sibyl's legend was possibly born from earthquakes.

But what about Queen Putry and the frightful, titanic, godly earthquakes that, across the centuries, have hit the Malay peninsula, Sumatra and the whole region of East Indies (the last in 2004, with its devastating tsunami)? Can any relationship exist between the legend and those ruinous natural events?

We don't know. But the wind gently blowing near the Princess' cave through the «thickets of bamboo, from which proceed harmonious voices and sounds of flutes and other musical instruments» cannot but remind us of the ominous, enraged winds flowing from the Sibyl's Cave when magical arts are performed there: a reminiscence, we saw in *The chthonian legend*, of the classical pre-scientific explanation of the origin of earthquakes.

And this surmise becomes almost a certainty when we read this excerpt drawn from the *Sejarah Melayu*:

«After some days, they reached the foot of Gunong Ledang and began the ascent of the mountain. And when they were about half way up, a wind arose so strong that they could climb no further and the path itself became exceedingly difficult. [...] And when they approached the 'singing bamboos', the climbers felt as though they were going to be blown away, so strong was the wind...».

then set out on the journey accompanied by Tun Māmad. And after some days, they reached the foot of Gunong Ledang and began the ascent of the mountain. And when they were about half way up, a wind arose so strong that they could climb no further and the path itself became exceedingly difficult. And Tun Mamad said to the Laksamana and Sang Stia, "Stay here, sir, all of you, while I go up." And when the Laksamana had agreed Tun Mamad went ahead with two or three men who were good walkers and continued the ascent with them. And when they approached the 'singing bamboos', the climbers felt as though they were going to be blown away, so strong was the wind: the clouds seemed so close as to be within their reach:

1952] *Royal Asiatic Society*.

Fig. 49 - The supernatural winds that are present in the legendary tale of Gunung Ledang, from C.C. Brown's translation of the *Sejarah Melayu* (*The Malayan Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, Vol. 25, parts 2 & 3, no. 159, 1953), p. 103

Because this excerpt is so similar, so ghastly similar, so strikingly similar to the ones we found in *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The paradise of Queen Sibyl*, which we presented in the papers *The chthonian legend* and *Four years from 'The chthonian legend'*:

«[...] but he had not got in because from the entrance's mouth he said that a great wind was blowing, so fierce that the very stones of the mountain could not resist to it».

[In the original Italian text: «[...] ma non era intrato dentro perché de la boca de la intrata disse che usciva si grande el vento che le pietre de la propria montagna non li poteva stare»].

Fig. 50 - The chthonian winds as they appear in Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Chapter CXXXIX in the edition printed in Venice in 1480)

«So they went through that narrower hollow, going ahead for some three miles, as they reckoned. Then they found a crevice which split the cave: a wind issued forth from the crevice, so horrible and astounding that no one of them dared to go ahead of a single step, or even half of it; because, when they tried to get nearer, they felt that the wind was trying to carry them away».

[In the original French text: «Allerent par ceste plus basse cave, tousdiz en avalant, bien l'espace de trois milles a leur advis. Lors trouverent une vaine de terre traversant la cave, dont ysoit un vent si treshideux et merueilleux que ne fut celui qui osast aler pas ne demy plus avant; car, aussi tost qu'ilz approchoient, leur sembloit que le vent les emportast»].

Fig. 51 - Subterranean winds as portrayed by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 10r and 10v)

Perhaps, the two legends - the Apennine Sibyl and Queen Putry - are not so independent as we assumed they were, earlier in the present article.

Perhaps, the soft winds at Gunung Ledang, too, may sometimes become dreadful storms, as the *Sejarah Melayu* seems to suggest; and, perhaps, they might mark the terrific presence of the seismic waves in the legendary tale of Queen Putry, too.

Just like it happens for our Sibyl of the Apennines.

Michele Sanvico